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**Towards a Gamified and Accessible Cultural
Heritage using Augmented Reality**

Thesis presented by

**Mennat Allah Salama Taha Ibrahim,
BSc. (Architectural Engineering)**

122105332

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School of Digital Arts and Humanities

Head of School/Department: Dr. Orla Murphy

Supervisor(s): Dr. Orla Murphy

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Declaration

“This is to certify that the work I am submitting is my own and has not been submitted for another degree, either at University College Cork or elsewhere. All external references and sources are clearly acknowledged and identified within the contents. I have read and understood the regulations of University College Cork concerning plagiarism and intellectual property.”

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Abstract

Learning about history and cultural heritage (CH) is shifting from its static non-interactive state into a more dynamic and engaging experience due to the adaptation of educational institutes such as Galleries, Libraries, archives, museums and schools (GLAMS) emerging technologies, gamification and multisensory design to create more attractive CH experiences that are inclusive and accessible to everyone (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 373).

Although different concepts of digitalization, accessibility and gamification have been addressed frequently in the CH field and based on observations and literature analysis their sub-features and elements often overlap, the absence of a holistic guideline that combines all these concepts for designers to enable them to attempt to form the optimum CH experience for All opens the doors for the possibility to create one. This research identifies a framework that combines elements of: digital cultural heritage, enjoyable informal learning, gamification in cultural heritage (CH), multisensory design, accessibility in CH and Augmented reality technology (AR) in order to create a holistic framework for Accessible Gamified Enjoyable Learning in CH using AR, that is implemented in the context of Egyptian CH that can be applied inside and outside museums with the intention of its usage globally.

The framework will be created from a combination of desk research, the analysis and reviewing of the literature of the areas concerned. The validity of the proposed framework is tested through three different experiments in the Egyptian CH context. The approaches outlined in the framework will be added gradually into the experiments as they progress and according to the needed elements in each experiment.

The first experiment creates a gamified accessible experience using AR which will be tested in the Modern Museum of Egyptian Art (MMEA), the second creating an AR scavenger hunt multisensory mobile game to be tested in the National Museum of Egyptian Civilization (NMEC) and the last experiment creates an AR CH tactile card game.

Introduction

“Though we see the same world, we see it through different eyes”

~ Virginia Woolf

Although we may experience the same events, we perceive them differently. Which was scientifically proven because our understanding of the surroundings depends on the process of sensation which is the input the physical environment received by our sensory receptors (eyes, nose, ears...etc.) and the process of perception which is the process by which our brains understand these inputs (A. Sanderson and College, 2022). That’s why different external stimuli like sound and light for instance, that can represent and construct part of a certain experience or event are perceived differently by different people (Alvarado *et al.*, 2011). Affecting how each person understands and feels the experience itself.

Which makes the job of designers challenging because their job is to create experiences that are positively perceived by a large number of people despite the varied impact they might have on them. i.e., they should design for all and include everyone in their designs taking into consideration the different stimuli that build the design experience itself i.e., creating multisensory designs to affect people’s perceptions and sensations during a certain experience.

CH experiences are no different, they require detailed and inclusive designs to influence their diverse audience. The importance of inclusive and accessible CH has been recognized by both the public and international organizations such as the UNESCO¹ because heritage should be accessed by everyone equally. (UNESCO, 2020). The accessibility of CH can be divided into the physical accessibility meaning creating universal designs to include people with disabilities and impairments in different CH experiences (Deffner *et al.*, 2015) and data accessibility which became feasible with the digital transformation of CH that lead to the creation of online collections and archives by many museums, galleries and libraries to ensure global access of culture (UNESCO, 2020). Not only did the digitization and the adaptation of technological

¹ UNESCO: The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

solutions in CH create inclusive and accessible environments but they have created engaging and enjoyable CH experience as well (Parsehyan, 2020). For instance the usage of immersive reality technologies such as virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) has added entertainment and gamification features to CH (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 478) by creating virtual immersive scenes and experiences increasing the memorability of the artifacts by the audience hence generating edutainment experiences associated with CH (Nofal *et al.*, 2018).

Although digital CH, gamification, informal learning, multisensory design and accessibility in CH have been addressed separately from scholars previously, it was observed by the researcher that these concepts frequently overlap and engage with each other in the context of CH.

Despite the fact that some scholars have created frameworks to achieve one or more of the concepts simultaneously, for instance scholars have create a framework for enjoyable informal learning using AR in the context of Indonesian CH (Chandini Pendit *et al.*, 2014, p. 21). Another scholar has created a framework for enjoyable CH for people with hearing impairments using AR (Baker, 2019). There has been no previous attempt to combine all the concepts together in order to create a holistic CH experience.

In this research an attempt to create a standardized guideline for creating a multisensory, accessible, gamified, enjoyable learning experience CH using AR to make it easier to design such experience in the future by following the guideline to ensure interactive CH for everyone is made by the researcher is relying on desk research and deep content analysis of the literature in order to identify common features between the main concepts mentioned that can be used in the framework. Afterwards, case studies are made in the context of Egyptian CH to test and validate the framework and assess the possibilities and limitations it may have in that context with the intention of its globalization. The case studies are created inside and outside the context of museums, where each one focuses on one or more sensory stimuli.

This thesis is structured as following; Chapter one represents an introduction to the research and a review of the literature in the areas addressing the implementation of digitalization, enjoyable informal learning, multisensory

design, gamification and Accessibility in the context of CH. Which represent the main concepts selected to analyze and study to create the holistic CH experience guideline.

Chapter two explains the technical process and the methodologies taken into creating the framework including desk research and literature analysis in order to identify the concepts repeated when addressing CH experience and creating the framework itself based on that analysis with the intention to validate and test it through three experiments in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter three “Living Paintings”; this chapter illustrates the implementation of some of CHx framework² features focusing on sound as a stimulus. It takes place at the online and offline context of the Museum of Modern Egyptian art and depends on the sonification and manipulation of its paintings to in order to create a novel memorable CH experience. A link to an online digital archive of part of the museum created by the researcher is included in this chapter.

Chapter four “AUGI”; this chapter presents a collaborative project indented to gamify the museum visit by creating an augmented reality scavenger hunt game at the National Museum of Egyptian Civilization in order to test more features of CHx framework with a focus on visual stimulus. A QR code to AUGI mobile application and the target images is included in this chapter as well.

Chapter five “c[AR]ds” presents a concept of creating a gamified accessible card game to take CH outside the walls of the museum and provide an inclusive CH enjoyable learning with the focus on the Haptic and olfactory stimuli.

Chapter six presents the conclusion and summery of the thesis.

² CHx framework: Represents the holistic CH framework created by the researcher in chapter two

Literature review

Literature Review Framework

The following diagram represents an overview of the literature review main concepts addressed in it.

Figure 1 Literature review framework

Digital Cultural Heritage

The rapid evolution of emerging technologies has enabled the transformation of the CH sector digitally, creating new opportunities that bring CH back to life and equipping CH sites and museums with the information and communication technologies (ICT) that increases the visitors' engagement and entertainment (Parsehyan, 2020) such as AR, Virtual Reality (VR), 3d modelling, 3d scanning and digital storytelling (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 474). These also facilitate the digital preservation of CH, and its accessibility to anyone at any time through the digitalization of tangible artifacts and the creation of online digital repositories of museum collections, virtual tours of existing physical museums and the creation of completely virtual museums (Hennessy, 2012, p. 346). The term Virtual Museum (VM) itself includes; mobile applications that explain history, on-site interactive installations which may involve re-construction of archeological and historical artifacts, web based VMs which provide VM tours and content via the web, multimedia VM which combine various interactive multimedia content of videos and audios...etc. through CDs and DVDs and digital archives which represent digital repositories of monuments collections mainly made for the sake of preservation and data accessibility (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 475).

On the other hand, physical museums have changed from being passive spaces that display artifacts into active engaging settings that create various storytelling and informal learning experiences to their visitors through hybrid interactions between the virtual and the physical worlds with the help of technological advancements such as; VR, which provides its users with fully immersed environments completely detached from the real world and AR, which mixes real and virtual worlds so that the users' senses are not separated from the real world (Mohammed-Amin, 2015, p. 22), i.e. it creates on-site interactive installations, for instance AR was used to create a virtual restoration experience at the Syracuse museum. (Kurosu, 2019, p. 448)

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 (a) The statue of Telamon at the Syracuse Museum. (b) Augmenting the 3D restored upper part of the statue on top of the physical statue (Stanco et al. 2012).

The idea of digital CH and the different types of VMs are to be combined together by the researcher in attempt to create an interactive AR mobile application that provides accessible multisensory content of the museums artifacts to increase its visitors' engagement by creating a hybrid experience that couples the virtual content to the physical museum monuments.

AR is often used to reveal more information about a museum's displays or the museum's environment itself and to provide interactive information about historical artifacts as well, via immersive audio-visual effects (Mohammed-Amin, 2015, p. 33). To overcome the museum visitors struggle to comprehend and to engage with the information associated with the museum's displays due to its small size, unclarity, or dullness (Kurosu, 2019, p. 448). For example; the [Terracotta Warriors](#) AR application illustrated in Figure 3 used in the Terracotta warriors Philadelphia exhibition, provides the visitors with scannable brochures and statues to see the augmented warriors and learn more about their history as the army of the first Emperor of China Qin Shi Huangdi (Mohammed-Amin, 2015, p. 31).

Figure 3 Augmentation scenarios from the Terracotta Warriors AR application (Mohammed-Amin, 2015, p. 31)

AR is also employed in creating a digital immersive storytelling experience. Figure 4 illustrates the usage of AR in describing and contextualizing a street museum using text and historic photos because the context of the historical events and environments represents a huge part of their stories (Mohammed-Amin, 2015, p. 33).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 Street Museum Application (a) Aligning a historic photo into the present real-view from a phone's camera. (b) Displaying the contextual information in text format about the historic photo. (Mohammed-Amin, 2015, p. 33)

Contextualization of CH

Museums provide a space for people to interact with and learn about the historical artifacts within their walls, however that communication is negatively influenced by the isolation and displacement of the artifacts from their original environments which causes loss in a lot of their spatial and contextual information³(Thompson, 1994). AR has been used to create an edutainment experience and increase the visitors' engagement and the memorability of the artifacts found in the Royal Museum of Art and History (RMAH) in Brussels by contextualizing one of the Assyrian⁴ artifacts there, which is the Genuis relief found in Figure 5 that was originally located in the Nimrud palace in Iraq by creating AR 3d modeled replica of the original room the artifact was found in Iraq and by evaluating the visitors experience before and after the artifact's contextualization.

Figure 5 (a) The relief of the Genuis head collected from Nimrud Palace (b) an abstract 3d visualization of reconstructing the original location of the RMAH artifact in the Nimrud Palace, and the surrounding architectural features (Nofal et al., 2018)

³ The context of the artifacts can be described as the original atmosphere of these historical items which includes the architectural context, i.e., the elements' design, the historical context which relates to the relation of an artifact to a specific event or time in history and the social context which describes the importance of an artifacts to people (Nofal et al., 2018).

⁴ Assyria refers to the kingdom of northern Mesopotamia that became the center of one of the great empires of ancient middle east. It was located in what is now northern Iraq and southeastern Turkey.(Augustyn, 2022)

It was found that the visitors had learned more and remembered the artifact's actual size and built environment after the AR contextualization experience as shown in Figure 6.(Nofal *et al.*, 2018)

Figure 6 (a) museum visitor using a tablet to experience the AR context of the Genuis Relief. (b) sample of the visitors sketches of the artifact based on their memory of its room found in the Nimrud Palace (Nofal *et al.*, 2018)

The previous case study indicates the importance of contextualizing the AR digital visualizations and content in order to create a memorable edutainment experience, which will be taken into consideration whilst designing the content of all the AR experiments that will be conducted in this research.

Enjoyable Informal Learning and Edutainment

Educational institutes such as schools, libraries, archives and museums (SLAMs) are responsible for the accessibility, preservation and distribution of CH knowledge. They have been changing their ways of teaching history and transforming themselves into living labs to engage their learners in edutainment and enjoyable informal learning⁵ processes (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 373). In the context of CH sites, it was found that the cognitive state and emotions of the CH sites visitors affect their ability to learn about history. In fact, the process of enjoyable informal learning mainly depends on three theories; (Chandini Pendit *et al.*, 2014).

⁵ Enjoyable informal learning refers to the learning process through which the learner doesn't feel that they are being taught whilst acquiring the information in a non-formally structured learning setting.

- 1- The enjoyment theory: *which refers to the engagement of a person in an activity that has a positive effect on him/her and giving that person a feeling of fulfillment and pleasure*(Lin et al., 2012).
- 2- The mindfulness theory: *which relates to the person's interest and care to the surrounding in which a positive stimuli is used to influence and attract the person's interest like the usage of various multisensory media, and creating novel and unpredicted experiences* (Moscardo, 1996, pp. 376–397.).
- 3- The enjoyable technology theory: *which refers to opportunities given by the technology to the user to actively participate in a challenging activity* (BRANDTZÆG et al., 2004, pp. 55–65).

The previous theories were used to create a guideline for enjoyable informal learning in CH sites that can be summarized in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Enjoyable informal learning in CH site (Chandini Pendit et al., 2014, p. 21)

The guideline was used to create a Mobile AR for Cultural Heritage Sites towards Enjoyable Informal Learning experience for the Prambanan Temple complex in Indonesia which is called: AR@Prambanan. The evaluation of the mobile app based on the user experience was a success and favored the implementation of the AR mobile applications to create informal learning experiences in CH sites and proved that multisensory dynamic multimedia enhances the visitors' responsiveness and learning. (Chandini Pendit et al., 2014, p. 25).

The success of such study provides us with a theoretical framework and a guideline that includes enjoyment, mindfulness and enjoyable technologies in order to create casual edutainment experience that truly affects the cognition and the engagement of the CH sites visitors. And will be implemented in the experiments performed in this research.

Gamification in CH

Gamification and serious games have been embraced by educational establishments including museums to enhance and engage the learners and visitors in an edutainment interactive learning process (Partarakis et al., 2017, p. 371). Gamification refers to the usage of game elements outside the games context (Du, 2020) where storytelling, points & rewards, achievement, timer, personalization and micro interactions are the most common gamification elements used in learning (Jackson, 2016). One example for gamified learning in CH is the Louvre Museum in Paris, which created a 3d audio guide that includes the museum artifacts in form of 3d models, high resolution images, videos in addition to audio and textual description of the displays, fun facts and back stories about them. The guide enables the visitors' interaction with the museum exhibits digitally by scaling and rotating them to see further details, in addition to allowing the virtual accessibility of the museum itself through virtual tours (Tieryas, 2017).

Serious games refers to applying simulations and games in non-entertainment context like the games used for marketing, health and educational purposes. (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 373). In case of museums games like scavenger hunts and puzzles are commonly used with mobile apps that guide the users to collect information about the artifacts displayed and solve tasks or quizzes related to the exhibits creating an enjoyable learning experience for the visitors (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 478) as mobile games are found to increase the museum visitors knowledge absorption without causing distractions (Maria, 2020).

AR mobile games are widely implemented in museums for their ability to engage people with the cultural content, it was suggested to create an AR mobile game in the Egyptian museum called "Horus" that educates the visitors

about the Egyptian gods through creating an AR battle scenario in one of the museum's actual halls between the ancient gods of Egypt of good and evil but it was never implemented. (Hammady et al., 2016, pp. 181–187). Another suggestion was to create a scavenger hunt mobile app in the Alexandria National Museum and although surveys were conducted that proved that such gamified experience will increase the visitors' number and engagement with the artifacts. (Elrouby and El Kasrawy, 2019).

One AR educational game in the CH sector outside the walls of museums is the "3D AR for Hukou Old Street" tabletop and mobile card game, created to immerse and teach its players about the ancient architectural elements and culture of the old Hukou street in Taiwan, the cards of the game are scanned by the game app to provide the players with 3d visualizations and information about the historic place. Not only does the game provide enjoyable informal learning process but it also creates a novel way of creating a cultural digital archive (Shih, et. al., 2015, pp. 387–394).

Figure 8 (a) 3D AR for Hukou Old Street tabletop game and game cards. (b) Scanning the door plate (left, the rear side of the board game card) to show further information about the building (right)

Figure 9 Scanning the front side of the board game card to

In this research a serious game is developed and its prototype is implemented as the first AR mobile game to be actually tested in an Egyptian museum. NMEC is chosen for testing in attempt to attempt to create a gamified immersive multisensory edutainment experience and increase the visitors' engagement and number in the museum. Also, inspired by the AR card game, this research will attempt to create a gamified multisensory AR tactile card game.

Multisensory Design

We as humans perceive the world around us using all of our senses; visual, hearing, smell, taste and touch. Moreover, the interaction of the senses affect our understanding of our surrounding environment (Partarakis *et al.*, 2017, p. 359). Mobile Technologies have facilitated the creation of multisensory content that has the potential to create a better and more inclusive CH experience for all (Mohammed-Amin, 2015, p. 22). For illustration, Mobile AR can provide information through visuals (Image, text...etc.), Audio animation and videos (Chandini Pendit *et.al.*, 2014, p. 20). Moreover, It was found that it's preferable to accompany museum journeys with olfactory and tactile elements that reflect upon and match the atmosphere of the displays for further visitors engagement and immersion (Ciolfi, 2021). One example is the case study of Palazzo dei Diamanti Museum in Italy in which a Mobile AR multisensory experience was created by adding animation to the paintings and using the paintings themselves as a marker for the AR and including the olfactory elements (3d printed sculptures) placed near some paintings, that produce smell when a visitor puts his/her hand on top of it, the scent produced is in harmony with its

accompanying painting mood. This is done to increase the visitors' memories of the museum and engagement with the paintings (Carulli and Bordegoni, 2020).

Figure 10 Architecture of the olfactory experience in Palazzo dei Diamanti the museum (Carulli and Bordegoni, 2020)

In fact, multisensory design was found to be correlated to learning because the more senses involved in the learning process, the more memorable the information becomes to the learners. Which is a theory that can be reflected upon museum visitors journey and the enjoyable informal learning that comes along with it in case of implementing proper interactive multisensory design (Harada *et al.*, 2018).

Multisensory design is also considered highly important for people with different disabilities, because adding or enhancing any sensory experience whether it's tactile, olfactory, auditory or visual can help in translating the surrounding data and environment into sensory media that can be experienced by people with various impairments including; hearing vision deficiencies (Thevin *et al.*, 2021).

From the literature review it is found that smell and taste the least included senses in the CH multisensory design. And when used, olfactory sense needs advanced gadgets to be used. In this research an attempt to create multisensory AR educational cards out of scented papers relevant to the card's CH content

will be experimented and will be displayed with oriental food that accentuates the smell and the whole theme of the card game.

Accessible CH

Many attempts have been made to make CH inclusive and accessible to anyone who wants to experience it. There are around 2.2 billion people with vision impairment around the world according to the World Health Organization (WHO) (Naranjo-Puentes *et al.*, 2022) whose condition affects their daily lives. CH mobile applications have tried to include people with vision and hearing disabilities in immersive museum experiences for example: (AI Museum) app which provides AR, screen reading of the content and customizable font size of the artifacts' description for the users which made art accessible for people with vision deficiencies and reading difficulties. (Guedes *et. al.*, 2020).

Figure 11 AI Museum user interface

Figure 12 AR Experience of a rapier in the AI museum App

Another accessibility helpful feature is physical/sound based/haptic feedback, i.e. Using the mobile vibrations to grab the users' attention (Naranjo-Puentes *et al.*, 2022). It was found that interactive maps and physical 3d models have a more satisfactory impact on people with vision deficiencies than silent tactile map and braille writings (Thevin *et al.*, 2021). The concepts of interactions, 3d models and physical/sound feedback were adapted by (Tooteko) which is a ring used by blind people to navigate tactile surfaces with their finger tips and returns back an audio content related to the part of the surface being touched. The below images show the implementation of the system on the facade of the church of S. Michele in Isola by Codussi, which represents the beginning of the Venetian Renaissance. This example illustrates the efficiency of the digitalization of data

and 3dprinting and how they can be integrated to create an inclusive small scaled-model (D'Agnano *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 13 (a) Tooteko system parts, (b) hotspots/NFC TAGS (D'Agnano *et al.*, 2015)

One attempt to make an AR museum experience accessible and engaging for people with hearing impairments is MARHIME⁶ which is mobile AR app developed by researchers at Ultra University in Malaysia, that proved the validation of the following framework which consists elements required for engaging people with hearing impairments in museum visits through mobile AR app:

- 1- Aesthetics: Refers to the beauty of the mobile app interface itself, it consists of elements of attraction, visual sense and the screen layout with a focus on the 3d models, images and associated text as hearing impaired people are highly attracted to visuals
 - 2- Usability: refers to the ease of the application usage and its functionality
 - 3- Interaction: refers to the user control over the app and the feedback it gives based on the user interaction
 - 4- Motivation: refers to the encouragement given to the user by the app
 - 5- Satisfaction: refers to the content and fondness of the users with the app
 - 6- Enjoyment: refers to the entertainment and fun of using the app
- (Baker, 2019, pp. 166–172)

⁶ MARHIME: Mobile Augmented Reality for the hearing-impaired museum engagement

From the case studies above the sensory elements and inclusion frameworks for people with hearing and vision difficulties will be analyzed in order to create the CHx framework.

Chapter 2

Methodology

Epistemology

The research arises from an observed need for the presence of a holistic framework that combines elements of digital CH, enjoyable informal learning, gamification, accessibility and multisensory design with technological solutions such as AR, in order to present an approach that can be used for projects that aim for a fun universal design in CH. This will be the first research of its kind in Egypt with the intention that it will be used as a pilot project to be further elaborated and implemented.

As the literature review has illustrated digitalization has helped in increasing the accessibility and the engagement with CH by digitizing artifacts and history (Hennessy, 2012, p. 346). It's essential to contextualize CH artifacts' to provide full understanding and immersion with them (Nofal *et al.*, 2018). Learning about history needs to be fun. In fact, an enjoyable informal learning framework was created by the researchers based on the enjoyment, mindfulness and the enjoyable technologies theories. (Chandini Pendit *et al.*, 2014). Gamification also contributes to interactive enjoyable learning (Jackson, 2016). Whilst Multisensory design was found to further enhance the learning experience in the context of CH as well (Harada *et al.*, 2018). It was also found to make information more accessible as it translates the data & environment into sensory media that is felt and experienced by people with certain impairments (Thevin *et al.*, 2021). Tactile elements are used to make CH accessible for people with vision deficiencies (D'Agnano *et al.*, 2015) and a model for an AR museum mobile application was created to include and engage people with hearing impairments in museum visits. (Baker, 2019).

The above literature summery shows connections and relations between, digital CH, its contextualization, enjoyable informal learning, gamification in CH, Multisensory design in CH and accessible CH which presents an opportunity to merge common elements of these features in order to create a holistic AR accessible multisensory gamified edutainment CH framework that can be applied inside and outside the context of museums and CH sites.

Research questions

Primary research question

1. Can we create a framework for Accessible Gamified multisensory Enjoyable Learning in CH using AR?

Secondary Research Questions

2. Can the framework be used inside and outside the context of the museum?
3. How can we validate such framework?
4. Is the framework valid in the Egyptian CH context?
5. Can the framework be used globally?

Aim

The aim of this research is to create a holistic standardized framework that can be used by anyone to design experiences that include learning about CH in an immersive and inclusive way using AR as a technological solution depending on research done before and cross referencing identified elements addressed in the literature review under the titles of: digital CH, edutainment & gamification in CH, multisensory design in CH and accessibility in CH. Then testing the validity of the framework through different experiments conducted in the context of the Egyptian CH with the intention of its global spreading. AR technology was chosen due its accessibility and affordability as it doesn't require special gadgets and depends mainly on cellphones.

Methodology

This research followed experimental, research by design and simulation methodologies because it depended on developing a hypothesis based on record keeping and analysis that was tested through the conduction of the three experiments outlined before for the purpose of improving the CH experience. A mixture of both qualitative and quantitative methods was used. The creation of the framework depended on desk research comprising secondary data collected from previously conducted research in relevant areas and primary data resulted

from the discourse and text analysis of the concepts mentioned in the literature review depending on the researcher’s observations and manual analysis of the content using tables and diagrams, the main variables and the connections and similarities found among their sub-features and elements were concluded based on the repetition of certain concepts and themes in the CH context.

The Framework creation

The CHx framework was derived from the researcher’s observations of the repetition of certain concepts, elements of design and features when searching about digital CH, edutainment & gamification in CH, multisensory design in CH and accessibility in CH. Which opened the door for the possibility to find the overlapping patterns between the main concepts addressed in this research. The framework was created in attempt to create a guideline for a better and inclusive CH experience, which is used to develop different case studies to validate and test the possibility of its implementation in different CH contexts.

The diagram presented in Figure 14 was created manually by the researcher depending on observation and analysis of the literature review in order to find the overlapping and similar elements in the concepts addressed. It consists of 6 main nodes that correspond to the main concepts that were concluded from the literature review and is color coded according to their sub-features overlapping. The following table represents a key for Figure 14

Table 1 Fig15 color key

Node Color	Meaning	Outline Color	Relevance
	Accessibility in CH main Node		Related to senses
	Accessibility in CH sub-Nodes		Related to accessibility
	Multisensory design in CH main Node		Related to fulfillment and achievement
	Multisensory design in CH sub-Nodes		Related to inclusive design
	Gamification in CH main Node		Related to technology in CH
	Gamification in CH sub-Nodes		Related to the user control
	Digital CH main Node		Related to game types
	Digital CH sub-Nodes		Related to enjoyable learning
	AR in CH main Node		Related to ordination and physical presence
	AR in CH sub-Nodes		Related to Multimedia
	Edutainment in CH main Node		Related to AR mobile applications
	Edutainment in CH sub-Node		

Figure 14 Diagram of the intersecting elements of different features addressed in this research in CH

Figure 16 diagram of another iteration of the connections of the nodes

The main components of the proposed CHx framework were decided based on the outcome of the desk research analysis of previous internationally benchmarked work. Building upon that and analyzing further the common sub-nodes of the main concepts which can be summarized in the following table:

Table 2 Summary of the main concepts and their overlapping features

Color	Main concepts	Overlapping / similar Features/elements
Orange	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Digital CH 2- AR 3- Edutainment & Enjoyable informal learning 4- Gamification in CH 5- Multisensory design in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Multimedia 2- digital storytelling 3- multisensory
Green	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Digital CH 2- AR 3- Multisensory design in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- AR mobile application 2- AR/VR & ICT
Red	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Digital CH 2- Accessibility in CH 3- Multisensory design in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Accessibility of CH 2- Digital & data accessibility 3- Strong visuals 4- Adjustable texts 5- Accessibility of CH & data transformation
Pink	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- AR 2- Edutainment & Enjoyable informal learning 3- Gamification in CH 4- Accessibility in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Enjoyment & Interaction 2- Info revealing 3- Edutainment 4- Enjoyment & enjoyable technologies 5- Interactive learning 6- Micro interactions
Brown	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- AR 2- Edutainment & Enjoyable informal learning 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Contextualization of the artifacts 2- Good physical orientation
Black	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- AR 2- Gamification in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- AR mobile games in CH
Blue	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Edutainment & Enjoyable informal learning 2- Gamification in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Feeling of fulfillment 2- Achievement & Fulfillment
Yellow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Edutainment & Enjoyable informal learning 2- Gamification in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Learner's/ user's control 2- Multiple opportunities 3- Personalization
Grey	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Gamification in CH 2- Accessibility in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Awards & Points 2- Motivation
Purple	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Multisensory design in CH 2- Accessibility in CH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Touch 2- Hear 3- Tactile experience 4- Haptic/Sound feedback

It was then found that the common nodes can be divided into features/ elements and outcomes that resulted in using those features which can be summarized in the following table:

Table 3 A more detailed analysis of the main concepts, their common features and the outcomes of using those features

Main Concept	Technologies	Features/ elements	Outcome
Digital CH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AR - VR - 3d modelling - 3d scanning - Digital storytelling - Mobile applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multimedia - VMs - Interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cultural preservation - Accessible CH - Informal Learning - Living museums
Contextualization of CH	AR mobile application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multimedia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in the visitor's engagement & memorability of the artifacts - Providing the correct info & context of the artifacts
Enjoyable informal Learning	AR mobile application	<p>(Mindfulness)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variety of media - User control - Connection with the user/ museum visitor - Good physical orientation - Novelty/Surprise - Use questions <p>.....</p> <p>(Enjoyable Tech. and Enjoyment)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variations & multiple opportunities - Social opportunities - Feeling of fulfillment - Feeling of pleasure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enjoyable informal Learning - Interactive Learning
Gamification in CH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobile applications - virtual guides 	<p>(Gamification elements in learning)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storytelling - Points & Rewards - Achievement - Timer - Personalization - Micro interactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edutainment - Interactive Learning - Engagement of the learners
	Mobile serious games	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Puzzles - Scavenger hunts 	

	- virtual guides	- Storytelling - Points & Rewards - Achievement - Timer - Personalization - Micro interactions	- Interactive Learning - Engagement of the learners
	Mobile serious games	- Puzzles - Scavenger hunts	
	AR card games	- Physical cards - 3d visualizations - Virtual information	- Enjoyable informal learning - Digital archiving
Multisensory Design	Mobile AR application	- Multimedia	- Fulfillment of the museum visitors/users - Increase in the visitors/ user's memorability of the information and artifacts
	Interactive installation	- Olfactory elements - Tactile elements	
		- Transformation of data into sensory media	- Enjoyable informal learning - Accessible CH
Accessibility in CH	AR mobile application	- Multimedia - Screen reading of the content - Font size customization	- Accessibility of data to people with vision & reading difficulties
		- Aesthetics - Usability - Interaction - Motivation - Satisfaction - Enjoyment	- Accessibility of data to people with hearing difficulties
	3D printing	- Sound/ haptic feedback - Tactile Experience	- Accessibility of data to people with vision difficulties

The above table proves that the CH experience can depend on three pillars; Technological Solution, Human interaction and the human response to that experience, meaning in order to create a holistic CH experience one must address the technology used, how people interact with it and how to include features that would make them feel and respond positively to it. It also proves that one feature can be used to achieve multiple concepts and can have multiple outcomes for instance the usage of “Multimedia” in CH is mentioned in almost

all of the six main concepts and has variety of outcomes regarding the user experience itself including: fulfillment, interaction, accessibility and enjoyment.

The following diagram illustrates the three pillars and the main concepts that are chosen to achieve them and present CHx framework which are technology, multimedia communication, interaction, motivation, fulfillment and enjoyment.

The main concepts and their sub-features are further illustrated in the diagram below. These concepts include: Technology with AR as a sub-element, Multimedia communication with sub-elements of Digital media, physical media and mixed media, Interaction including user control of the experience, multiple choice and opportunities provided to the user and hybrid interaction, Motivation with the help of a surprise factor, points/ rewards, personalization of the experience and social interaction, Fulfillment gained by the senses of achievement and happiness and the connection between the user and the experience itself and lastly, Enjoyment which depends on storytelling, entertainment and good physical orientation.

Figure 17 Diagram of CHx framework

In the following chapters the framework and its sub-concepts are addressed in more depth and specific elements are added to them in order to design different holistic fully engaging CH experiences. Each experience focuses on one main sensory element with supporting minor ones, the first one focuses on the hearing sense the second on the visual one and the last on the haptic one.

Chapter 3

The Living Paintings Experiment

The Process

Introduction

The Living paintings experiment was done in attempt to create a multisensory gamified CH experience with a focus on audio-visual effects. AR technology was chosen as a method to experience the multimedia visualization that rely on universal design to engage all the visitors of the Museum of Modern Egyptian Art (MMEA)⁷ with the existing paintings inside it, when they either visit the museum in person or access the gallery's displays online. CHx framework was used as a guideline to create the holistic CH experience.

MMEA itself withholds around 10,000 paintings and statues that showcase the development of the art movement in Egypt from the 20th century till our present day and is considered an important exhibition for the modern Egyptian art.

Overview and CHx framework

The following diagram illustrates the CHx framework features that were selected for implementation in this project with sub-elements added to achieve those concepts. The concepts chosen for implementation are in their original colors whilst those that are not are dimmed in dark grey color.

The shape represents the elements chosen specifically in this experiment in order to achieve the goals and how to measure their implementation and success.

⁷ The Museum of Modern Egyptian Art is also known as the Gezira Center for Modern Art and the Egyptian Modern Art Museum. It is a part of the National Cultural Center, along with the Cairo Opera House.

Figure 18 Detailed diagram of CHx framework implemented in The Living Paintings experiment

The previous diagram summarizes the technical flow of the living painting experiment based on the Chx framework. For the technological aspect Artivive AR platform is used due to its ease in usage as it requires no experience in programming to use. The platform consists of an online editor that enables uploading the target images, multimedia content used and revealed upon scanning and the Artivive mobile application which is used to scan the target images in accordance with the ones used in the online platform and enables the user to enjoy various AR experiences once he/she registers and it also has the video recording and sharing options of the experience and The success of the AR tech itself depends on the usability of the app and smooth running of the AR experience multimedia.

The multimedia communication is divided into three types the digital one which uses text, image, audio and animation in the AR experience where Arabic and English Text annotations are add to the paintings in the digital archive, images of the paintings are added to the archive as well, in addition to adding animation to the AR experience. The success of the digital media implementation depends on the user's appeal of them, their functionality and clarity.

The physical one which is represented in the mobile phones or tables used by the participants and is assessed by their willingness to download the required app. The last one is the mixed media that relies on the transformation of data into different senses for instance hearing data "sound" will be transformed into animation and sound visualization "to be experienced by the sense of vision". visual data will be transformed into sound "hearing sense" and their success will depend on the participants engagement and realization of the data converted.

The participant's interaction is achieved by giving him/her the control of the experience and the freedom to interact with the paintings as they wish and is assessed accordingly. In addition to providing the user with hybrid interaction through the communication between the physical and digital world and is measured by the level of immersion and communication with the experience and the user's interest in continuing the experience.

The user's motivation is spiked by the surprise factors created by unexpected multimedia and the users' invitation for social interaction and sharing their experience on social media which is assessed by the users' surprise level,

memorability of the experience, and willingness to share their experience on social media.

The fulfillment of the participants is achieved by the sense of happiness they get from learning something new about MMEA artifacts and having a new experience and is evaluated by the scale of the participants satisfaction.

The enjoyment is accomplished by adding entertainment elements through various multimedia to induce curiosity and interest, by providing a novel experience through the implementation of AR technology to the experience and by making sure that the placement of the painting is appropriate and comfortable to the user. The scale of the user's entertainment and the ease of the user's interaction with the paintings evaluate the enjoyment.

Research and concept

This experiment focuses on the sound and its visualization as multimedia elements that act as stimulating and engaging factor to the museum visitors and testing the potentials of applying sonification within the context of the museum, which refers to the process of converting data into sound and exploring the opportunities that emerge when combining sonification with AR and sound visualization. One of the most recent interesting applications is the [sonification of space](#) done by Nasa in which various data of nebulae, black holes and galaxies are converted into sound. (Vogel, 2020).

The experiment depends on image sonification which is the process of converting data in images "usually the brightness and darkness of the pixels found in the image" into sound waves in which the different frequencies correspond to the saturation of the pixels, higher frequencies mean lighter pixels.

A 4-layered visualization is done in the design in attempt to transform the museum paintings into from static displays into living art through the image manipulation and animation of the existing paintings, sonification of the paintings to generate sound from their pixels, then visualizing this sound and unveiling the full experience using AR technique which is illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19 conceptual illustration of the living painting experiment implemented on the context of the Mona Lisa Painting

The Mona Lisa painting was chosen to illustrate the main design concept and testing found in Figure 19 &

Figure 20 due to its popularity. The initial sonification testing was done using two software which are:

- 1- [Photo sounder](#):

It decodes the noise found in the image based on the pixels. It converts the images into spectrograms⁸ (Tipp, 2018).

⁸ Spectrograms are types of Waveforms that are in fact a type of graph, with time on the X axis and amplitude (or loudness) on the Y-axis (Tipp, 2018).

Figure 20 screen shot of the Mona Lisa painting in photo sounder and its conversion to audio

Figure 21 Illustration of an audio graphs (spectrograms) showing the amplitude & the frequency

2- [Pixelsynth](#):

It's a browser-based synthesizer that transforms the image into grey scale and then uses it to create a sine wave creating what's called by Olivia Jack" it's creator" the noise of art. The application reads any white information on the black background as note-on. The velocity of the note is dependent on the transparency of the object and pitch depends on its location - at the base of the picture for the low tones, etc.

Figure 22 Stairway to pixelated-noise heaven, screen shot of pixelsynth

Implementation and Analysis

The preliminary testing of the image sonification concept was done on the Mona Lisa created by Leonardo Da Vinci and the Broadway Boogie-Woogie Painting by Piet Mondrian found in Figure 23. The two paintings were chosen due to their popularity, different styles and color moods and orientation for instance, the Mona Lisa is a rectangular realistic portrait with neutral earthy colors and The Broadway painting is a square abstract painting with vibrant colors and high contrast.

Following the testing, the two paintings are intended to be used as a pilot case study in the sonification of the MMEA paintings.

(a)

(b)

Figure 23 (a) Mona Lisa Painting (b) Broadway Boogie-Woogie Painting

A comparison of the two paintings sonification audio was done using photo sounder and pixelsynth software found in Table 4. Omeka platform was used as an archival host for the paintings' images themselves and their associated meta data and Soundcloud was used as an audio hosting platform for the audio files.

Table 4 A comparison of The Mona Lisa and The Broadway Paintings sonification

Painting Name	Omeka Link	Audio produced via Photo Sounder	Audio Produced Via Pixelsynth
Mona Lisa created by Leonardo Da vinci	https://archive.mennasalama.org/cms/items/show/1	https://soundcloud.com/menna-salama-441764573/mona-lisa?si=785226badffc4153b1c62b1069ae7a6a&utm_source=clipboard&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=social_sharing	https://soundcloud.com/menna-salama-441764573/mona-lisa-1?si=03211599f8e44845a50739b2e388b8b8&utm_source=clipboard&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=social_sharing
Broadway Boogie-Woogie Painting by Piet Mondrian	https://archive.mennasalama.org/cms/items/show/3	https://soundcloud.com/menna-salama-441764573/broadway-boogie-woogie_photosounder?si=d73df5dc68324514b84e60fc8b97b1a6&utm_source=clipboard&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=social_sharing	https://soundcloud.com/menna-salama-441764573/broadway-boogie-woogie_pixelsynth?si=d73df5dc68324514b84e60fc8b97b1a6&utm_source=clipboard&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=social_sharing

Initial Testing Results:

- 1- By testing each of the two paintings in the two different software separately, the output audio was different each time proving that each software works differently and the difference in the paintings hues and pixel colors have affected the audio generated.
- 2- The ratios/dimensions of the images were distorted once imported into both software resulting in an inaccurate sonification since the number and distribution of the paintings' pixels have changed in the software. The below images illustrate the distortion and stretching that happened in the Mona Lisa image once imported in Pixelsynth and photo sounder, both of them has caused the transformation of the image orientation from being a regular portrait position into rectangular landscape position but with different stretching ratios.

Figure 24 Screen Shot of Mona Lisa Painting in Pixelsynth

Figure 25 Screen shot of the Mona Lisa painting in pixelsynth

- 3- The output of both the Mona Lisa and the Broadway images' sonification is more of a noise/glitching rather than a pleasant sound.

Initial testing conclusion:

- 1- Pixelsynth and photo sounder will not be used in the sonification "sound embedding" in the MMEA paintings due to the noise resulted from using them.
- 2- Methods of converting the images data into piano notes or any other pleasant music to hear will be tested in future work instead of the noise created by sonification using pixelsynth and photo sounder tools.
- 3- The potential of encoding an audio narration or a story in museum paintings that can be listened to by people upon scanning a certain encoded node in the painting or a QR code accompanied with sound animated visualization of the audio will be taken into consideration.
- 4- The potential of including a transcription of the audio to be revealed in the AR experience will be taken into consideration. This is intended to create an

inclusive attractive museum experience for all the visitors where visitors with hearing impairments can read the transcriptions associated with the paintings and engage with the animated sound visualizations to feel more connected and involved with the art itself.

MMEA Living Paintings

From the previous experiment, the idea The MMEA Living paintings project was created. Initially site visits to the museum were conducted in order to get a good understanding of the museum and its displays. The museum consists of three floors that contain various paintings and sculptures. Initially, it was intended to create the experiment onsite and then implement it online by integrating the AR experience to the digital archive of the paintings.

However, it was concluded from the site visit that the museum had no website and no digital archive. And based on observations, not all the museum displays were properly curated and included the artists' names and the year of the artwork creation.

Figure 26 image of MMEA museum interior(Cairo 360, 2018)

The absence of the MMEA online presence resulted in the researcher's decision to create an online digital archive of the museum for the purposes of digital preservation and digital accessibility of data starting by the artifacts found on the ground floor of the museum. Later, the living painting experiment will be implemented on those paintings testing the CHx framework.

The Archive Making

The archive was done manually by the researcher by conducting site visits and taking pictures of the paintings and documenting their information found in their associated info tags found in the museum. The images and information were then sorted and upload to flourish platform which is an online data visualization platform, in order to create an easy to navigate, visually appealing multimedia content. The card style was chosen as it was found most suitable to create the archive that consists mainly of rectangular images and text.

The archive consists of an image of each artifact with its name in both Arabic and English on it to ensure its accessibility, its providence of a fulfilling learning experience and its availability for re-usage. It's color-coded where according to the artists' names, with the artists names legend at the top. The order of the artifacts in the archive corresponds to their actual order of placement in the museum from right to left in the display hall. Below is the link to the flourish visualization of the archive:

<https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/10982333/>

Figure 27 Screen shot of the digital archive

Paintings Manipulation

In order to create a living painting from the archive, Yousef Kamel's "A Rural Girl" painting was selected to start with as it's the first artifact in the archive. Animation was added to it using "HitPaw" platform which is an online AI face animator used to create an animation of the still image, "Veed.io" which is an online audio visualizer was then used to add audio visualization to the video, and at last "Artivive bridge" which is an online AR platform was used to create an AR surprising experience of the painting that would motivate people. Link of the full experience can be found below:

<https://youtube.com/shorts/2vJNon2ismM?feature=share>

To activate the AR image download ARTIVIVE mobile app and scan the original image "rural girl image", P.S. you need to be connected to the internet for it to work.

Figure 29 Yousef Kamel's original "A rural Girl" painting

Figure 28 Yousef Kamel's "A rural Girl" painting after being manipulated using "HitPaw" an AI online face animator

Figure 30 Yousef Kamel's "A rural Girl" after using VEED.IO online sound visualizer

Figure 31 Yousef Kamel's "A rural Girl" after using Artivive AR App

Conclusion and Future Work

The experiment has successfully applied the features and main concepts selected from CHx framework in Figure 18 and was implemented on one painting which can be experienced inside the walls of the museum or outside it through the online archive, proving that the framework points selected can be implemented in the context of the Egyptian Heritage whether it's online or offline.

However, the experiment didn't succeed to address every concept in the framework, further attempts will be made in the following experiments in order to achieve the wholistic CH experience. And since this experiment was focusing on the sense of hearing, the sense of vision will be focused on in the next experiments in order to test different sensory approaches.

Manipulating modern art into fun non-static digital media at MMEA creates a new prospect which might actually be appealing to viewers and encourage younger generations to visit the museum and or learn more about the art onsite

and online. However, Older generation may find it challenging to use the AR technology and navigate the online archive. And this is to be confirmed in the future after conducting user testing and feedback on a large sample of people.

In case of the online environment, participants won't struggle in aiming their phones towards the artifacts to unveil the AR experience but it can be a bit challenging in the actual museum context because a lot of factors can affect the experience including the artifact and the visitor "mobile camera" orientation and the lighting of the indoor environment for instance. Consequently, several recommendations and guidelines are to be suggested to the museum to ensure the smooth-running of the AR experience, for example placing guides on the floor that would mark the appropriate user standing distance and position from the artifact or adding frames to some displays to ensure a correct camera orientation between the visitor and the artifacts.

Figure 32 illustration of the AR guides on the displays

Figure 33 illustration of the AR guides on the floor

Using Artivive as the AR platform created a fast and easy to use AR solution however some features including scaling and rotating the virtual data were missing resulting in the intention to explore different more flexible AR solutions in the future that gives the user more control over the environment. Also, it's intended as a future work to Complete the digital archive to include all the MMEA's artifacts and to manipulate the rest of the archival components in order to give the user multiple choices of the experience and more freedom in the digital interaction. A Transcription of the audios used as multimedia elements is to be added to engage people with hearing deficiencies and create a more engaging and inclusive experience. And the possibility of collaborating with be [my eyes mobile](#) application is to be investigated. Which is a mobile app that allows volunteers to narrate their experience to the visually impaired, maybe a specific narration of the museum can be added to the app.

Chapter 4

AUGI

**Extend Your Reality
Experiment**

The Process

Introduction

AUGI is another experiment done applying features of the CHx framework features in the context of the NMEC in order to create a fully engaging and memorable CH experience using AR and in attempt to confirm the legitimacy of the framework usage indifferent contexts using different features and concepts of the guideline itself. This experiment is designed mainly for implementation within the museum walls itself, focusing more on visual effects as multimedia sources. It's an extended reality scavenger hunt mobile game intended to create a museum within a museum fresh experience. The experiment itself was done collaboratively between fellow MA students; Mirhan Ayman and Rana Akeel and myself.

NMEC 's considered a cultural and educational hub, it's the first museum in Egypt that provides the visitors with a view of the different eras and civilizations that encompassed Egypt, starting from the predynastic era all the way towards our modern era, that's why it attracts a lot of international and national researchers. It had gained a lot of popularity during the last year after the pharos' Golden Parade happened in 2022 when 22 mummies were moved from the Egyptian museum including mummies of King Rameses the second, Queen Hatshepsut and many more. (NMEC, 2021)

Overview and the framework

The following diagram illustrates the CHx framework features that were selected for implementation in this project with sub-elements added to achieve those concepts. The concepts chosen for implementation are in their original colors whilst those that are not are dimmed in dark grey color

The shape represents the elements chosen specifically in this experiment in order to achieve the goals and how to measure their implementation and success.

Figure 34 Illustration of the CHx framework features used in AUGI experiment

All the virtual multimedia features are also measured by their relevance to the artifact used as targets themselves in order to provide an engaging experience, their scale "their coverage of the desired parts of the Target image and their resolution"

The previous diagram summarizes the technical flow of the AUGI experiment based on the Chx framework. For the technological aspect Vuforia package for Unity 3d is used, Vuforia enables the creation of an image dataset that consists of images of the museum artifacts that can be used as target images and markers for revealing multimedia and communication content upon scanning, Vuforia was used due to the flexibility of the features it provides like scaling and rotating the virtual content and the diversity of the AR options it provides including image targeting, 3d object tracking and 3d object placement and The success of the AR tech itself depends on the usability of the app and smooth running of the AR experience multimedia.

The multimedia communication is divided into three types the digital one which Includes, Text; which represents the annotations of the artifacts in the AR scenes, the onboarding text explaining the game and is measured by the comprehensibility of the text by the users and their understanding of the game. Images; which represent the image targets used and the infographics used as onboarding screens and their success is measured by the clarity of the image targets that would lead to the ease of image detection upon scanning and the visitors' fondness of the infographics and understanding of the game rules. Animation and videos which represent different AR scenes and Gifs that are unveiled by the users upon scanning, in addition to the music added to those scenes where the success of each's implementation depends on the user's appeal of them, their smooth running and in general, all the virtual multimedia features can also be assessed based on their relevance to the artifact used as targets themselves in order to provide an engaging experience. Also, visual AR multimedia can be assessed based on their virtual scale "whether they cover the desired parts of the Target images or not? and the quality of their resolution".

Physical multimedia is represented in the mobile phones or tables used by the museum visitors and is assessed by their willingness to download the required app. The last one is the mixed media that relies on the transformation of data into different senses for instance transforming text found in the onboarding screens into and the annotations in the AR scenes into narrations and sound data and its success depends on the participants' engagement and understanding of the data, artifacts and the game play even if they have

illiteracy struggles. *(This option was planned for implementation in the final mobile app version and not the MVP⁹ presented in this research).* As well as transforming the visual data into tactile data by creating tactile information panels in front of the museum displays where the inclusion of visitors with vision deficiencies and their understanding of the data/ artifact engraved in the information panels is a measurement for its success. *(This was planned for installation at the museum but still pending the museum approval).*

Figure 35 illustration of tactile information panels at museums (Johnson, 2022)

The participant's interaction is achieved by allowing the participants to be in charge of their actions towards the museum tour, the mobile application, how

⁹ MVP: Minimum Viable product

to start the tour and which artifacts to collect and is measured by the scale to which the participants feel free and in charge of their experience. In addition to distributing the artifacts selected in the AR experience in different zones in the museum to give the players their own tour choice and various opportunities “artifacts” to collect to complete their journey. And this is measured by analyzing the different artifacts collected by different players. In addition to providing the users with hybrid interaction through the communication between the physical and digital world and is measured by the level of immersion and communication with the experience and the users’ interest in continuing the experience.

The user’s motivation is spiked by the surprise factors created by unexpected multimedia, providing incentives to the players from the museum gift shop when they finish the game and the satisfaction of the players by the rewards/points themselves are assessed. The users’ invitation for social interaction and sharing their experience on social media and is assessed by the users’ willingness to interact together, their memorability of the experience, and willingness to share their experience on social media. Moreover, the players’ experience is personalized by allowing them to create their own avatars that will guide them through the game and the diversity of the avatars created and their reflection on the players real personalities are analyzed (*this is also planned for the final product not the MVP*).

Participants feel the sense of fulfillment by gaining the senses of achievement and happiness and creating a connection between them and the CH experience through completing the game itself and learning something new and bringing the museum to life and connecting the visitors with the museum and the experience itself respectively. These features are evaluated by the number of players who actually finish the game, scale of the participants satisfaction, their learnability of the artifacts, and the scale to which they feel connected to their museum experience and the game.

The enjoyment is accomplished through storytelling and creating a storyline for the game itself and for the AR scenes used and is measured by the participants understanding of the game, artifacts and their original story. In addition to adding entertainment elements by using various multimedia to induce curiosity and interest, as well as providing a novel experience through the

implementation of AR technology to the experience and by making sure that the placement of the painting is appropriate and comfortable to the user. The scale of the user's enjoyment and the ease of the user's interaction with the artifacts evaluate the enjoyment.

Research and Concept

This experiment focuses on visual multimedia components as part of a new AR CH experience to be implemented in the context of Egyptian museums. NMEC was chosen as a field for the study due to its large capacity and diversity in the displays from various eras providing a rich environment for experimentation. Initially, site visits were conducted to the museum and Several meetings were conducted by the research team with the museum administrators for the purposes of data collection, project concept development and to gain full understanding of the museum's-built environment and the potentials it may have. The data collected was a mix of data relevant to the artifacts and the monuments themselves and their history, and data related to the museum regulations and the experiment limitations, the data collected can be summarized as following:

- 1- NMEC's administration support the adaptation of new experiences in their museum. However, no monuments were allowed to be removed from their closed display for closer examination.
- 2- Most of the monuments are found in glass displays of high clarity.
- 3- Not all the monuments are presented in the museum galleries, there are a lot found in its storage which are not accessible to the public.
- 4- The museum holds multiple cultural events and welcomes a lot of school trips.
- 5- The museum consists of indoor halls, only one gift shop and two cafeterias, in addition to an outdoor theatre and an exterior open space.
- 6- There are four indoor exhibition halls at NMEC which are:
 - a- The main hall: which exhibits a variety of monuments from the predynastic era to the pharaonic era moving to the roman ones and the Islamic and contemporary ones
 - b- The Mummies Hall: which exhibits real mummies of pharaonic kings and queens (*N.B Taking photos is not allowed in this hall*).

- c- Eduardo Tuda hall (Temporary Hall whose content changes regularly, it was exhibiting Eduardo Tuda’s journeys at the time of our visits): which exhibits the journey of Eduardo Tuda who has done a lot of excavation journeys in upper Egypt
- d- The Textile Hall: which exhibits the art and crafts of the textile industry in Egypt throughout the years.

Table 5 summery of the museum halls

The hall	The hall Picture	Notes
The main Hall	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 36 Image of NMEC’s main hall</i></p>	It’s the biggest hall in the museum with the largest number of artifacts, and it contains artifacts from different civilizations that existed in Egypt starting from the predynastic era, moving towards the kingdoms’ era, then the roman and the Greek one towards the Islamic era and finally the modern era
The Mummies Hall	-	Taking photos is not allowed in this room
Temporary hall	<p>The hall content is temporary changes frequently to include different exhibits.</p> <p>Upon some of our site visits it included Eduardo Tuda’s Gallery and after that the hall was closed for preparation for a different gallery.</p>	<p>It’s pretty small in comparison to the other museum halls</p> <p>It’s more of a photos and paintings gallery that document the excavations of Eduardo Tuda</p>

<p>The Textile Hall</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 37 Image of NMEC's textile hall</i></p>	<p>It's a double height hall with two floors.</p> <p>Its main content is the history of the textile industry in Egypt.</p>
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- 7- The main hall consists of multiple interactive screens used by the visitors to learn more about the artifacts and display screens that are continuously playing historical videos about the museum collections.

Figure 38 Example of the interactive and display screens found in the museum

- 8- There is no virtual tour guide provided by the museum however, NMEC is the first museum Egypt to have its own mobile application.
- 9- There are plans to include people with disabilities in the museum not only as visitors but also as employees and tour guides.
- 10- There is a huge part of the museum that's still under construction and inaccessible for our experimentations.

After the data collected brainstorming sessions and research were done by the researchers for the purpose of concept development of the project. As a group project each researcher had her own goals to achieve out of it; I was interested

in holistic CH experiences, Mirhan was interested in Egyptian monuments preservation and Rana was interested in orientalism and artificial intelligence (AI). Having different interests to get out of the same project made it challenging to try and develop a concept that would meet such diverse requirements.

AUGI “Extend Your Reality”

Based on the research mentioned in the literature review and the research team discussions it was decided to create a project that includes various museum artifacts in order to meet all the researchers’ interest, and since the main hall of the museum contains the largest number of artifacts, has the highest visitors’ traffic and include screens that can be used to explain and promote AUGI among visitors, it was chosen as a place for the experiment. After that it was decided to create AUGI which is a scavenger hunt AR mobile game that will be implemented at NMEC as a pilot project and upon its completion can be used in other CH environments which aspires to create a museum within a museum experience meaning it intends to create a new and immersive museum experience inside the existing museum without changing its original state in fact it reveals the hidden beauty within its walls and the stories behind its artifacts and create a new representation of the information and context associated by the artifacts while creating an edutainment visitors’ experience through hybrid interactions created by AR where visitors are to scan different artifacts in order to experience and collect the virtual scenes and objects and gain incentives afterwards. AUGI is to be applied in the museum’s main hall as an initial phase with the intention of its extension in the other halls later on.

The Players’ Journey

The choice of the treasure hunt was to gamify the visitors’ experience in an engaging way, through which the players go through the player to go through diverse artifacts found along the main hall and represent different civilizations that existed in Egypt to complete the game. The below image illustrates the organization of the different civilizations in the main hall.

Figure 39 illustration of the civilizations' organization in the main hall

The journey is also designed to direct the visitors through the main hall to collect virtual surrogates of the existing artifacts.

Figure 40 The initial suggested user journey by the design team

The artifacts selected for the hunt can be divided into main artifacts which are The Sabil, The Nubian House, The Description of Egypt book which are found in Islamic and Egyptian part of the hall, these artifacts were selected as primary ones due to their high value and poor representation in the museum. Based on observations conducted during the site visits and dialogues done with the museum managers, it was concluded that these artifacts were considered dead zones with little to no visitors traffic and low interest regardless of their high value. Because the Sabil and the Nubian house were presented as static grey mock-ups that don't explain the story behind them fully and the description of Egypt book was presented in a glass display with no possibility for the visitors to flip its pages.

Figure 41 Sabil Mockup on the left image and on the right, we can see the Nubian house mock-up found in the museum

Figure 42 The Description of Egypt book

The secondary artifacts were selected to familiarize the visitors/players with CH by engaging them with daily-life artifacts, i.e., including chairs, baskets, jewelry and cosmetics as items to be collected in the hunt. This concept plans to connect the players with the displays outside the normal notion of history, it gives the players the perspective that we are living in our future CH and CH is not something that had existed in the past and now is over, in fact it's something that is continually evolving and taking parts in our lives. Initially, the game was designed so that each item of the secondary artifacts represents one point in the game and their progress can be checked using a progress bar in the game itself while the primary artifacts represent 2 points and the players are to collect 3 artifacts from each era found in the main hall during their hunt in order to complete the game. The following images represent the initial secondary artifacts selected for the game.

Figure 43 writing equipment, Chair, Memorial set from left to right

Figure 44 Water cleansing, Baskets, Boxes from left to right

Figure 45 cosmetics set, water container, grains container from left to right

Figure 46 Mosaic Floor, Lighting fixtures, Music instruments from left to right

The Extended Reality

The choice of the extended reality was to create a fully immersed user experience. Virtual reality (VR) was suggested first by our team but it was not welcomed by the museum due to the regulations that banned the usage of the VR headsets in the museum since COVID-19 also to prevent the users from crowding or waiting in line to use the VR gadgets.

It was then decided that AR is more feasible since all the visitors can use their cellphones to scan markers represented in; QR Codes, Images, artifacts.... etc. to unveil a virtual experience to collect the items required in the treasure hunt. Furthermore, AR represents a flexible medium to add dynamic interactive multisensory content without detaching its user from the physical environment.

The Incentives

Initially it was suggested that during the user's journey of AR artifacts hunt, a jigsaw is created with missing pieces that are completed upon the collection of items that reveals an animated 360 virtual scene that tells an unfamiliar story to the players. Later on, discussions have been made with the museum to add gift cards as incentives as a motivation to those who finish the game as an attempt to increase the gift shop revenue as well. Another discussion was made in regard of creating mini quizzes that show up after the player scans a certain item to make sure that the player was paying attention to the information displayed in the AR experience, in this case the incentive will be based on the player's success in the quiz.

AUGI Storyboard

The following diagram summarizes AUGI's storyboard that includes the onboarding and the marketing that will be done by the museum in order to familiarize the visitors with the game idea and rules, by including banners and game guides in the museum itself and a QR code that enables the visitors to download AUGI and start looking hunting the artifact

STORYBOARD

* Visitors enter the museum

* Visitors view game icons on their first touch point; banners or interactive screen at the entrance

* They scan the code with their mobile phones

* They open the game guide through the App.

* They open the Game on the Mobile Application

* They enter the main hall (level 1) and start picking the artefacts to scan and collect

* Visitor scans the music instruments

* They listen to the music and sees AR sound visualizations

* They move to other artefacts

* The Cave

* Cosmetics

* Chair

* Papyrus and writing equipment

* Water and cleansing equipment

* Mosaic Wall

* Water and drinks Containers

* Boxes and Baskets

* Lanterns

* Books

* Scan the Sabeel

* Virtual Version of Sabeel

* Scan the Nubian House

* Virtual version of Nubian House

* The visitor goes to other halls to continue the game

Figure 47 illustration of AUGI storyboard

Implementation and Analysis

Since AUGI's experiment is intended to test the CHx framework with a focus on the visual sense, a lot of effort was done to enhance the visual virtual AR experience of the game. Equal contributions were made by the research team members in order to design the virtual scenes from the initial artifacts' selection to modeling, texturing and animation where each team member was responsible for the virtual creation a number of artifacts. However, all the design concepts and the ideation parts were done collaboratively.

The AR scenes were designed and created in relevance to the actual artifacts with the intention to allow the user to learn more about the artifacts in an entertaining way using diverse virtual multimedia creating a sense of happiness and achievement to the user. For instance, some scenes contain animation, others contain 3d static models, others contain music, some contain 2d animations and some contain reconstruction of the artifacts. This is done to test the users' response and engagement with the different multimedia and to provide them with different experiences that spike their interest.

Initially we wanted to use 3d object tracking in order to create 3d experiences that overlays the existing 3d artifacts of the museum, however the museum regulations didn't allow the 3d scanning of the artifacts, so we wanted to test the possibility of using 2d images as markers to track 3d objects. A small experiment was done by the research team on a chair found on a campus using Artive platform by which a 2d image of the chair was used to detect the 3d chair, the [experiment](#) proved that this was actually possible however the detection was glitchy and unstable.

Figure 48 Illustration of the AR 3d object tracking using 2d image through Artivive platform

After the experiment we consulted AR experts on the matter and we were advised to choose monuments that are somehow planar without much 3d details and to switch to unity 3d and Vuforia in order to get a better result if we wish to create AR that overlays the existing object (*use image targeting*) and that if we are to deal with more complicated and detailed models then it was better to use AR foundation and create a placement of the virtual models instead. The preparation of the virtual scenes was done in parallel to field testing of the AR to optimize the user experience.

Starting with the main artifacts the first step was to collect the images that will be used as image targets to the AR and Test these images to proof the possibility of the AR creation using Unity, Vuforia and AR foundation. The following images illustrate the results of the detection testing done on the Primary Artifacts at the museum proofing the concept and the possibility of creating different AR experiences in the museum using image targeting of simple artifacts and model placement for more complex ones.

1- [The Nubian House Detection](#)

Figure 49 Image detection of the Nubian House at NMEC

2- [The Book of Egypt Detection](#)

Figure 50 The Description of Egypt Book image detection at NMEC

3- [The Sabil AR Foundation testing](#)

Figure 51 Sabil model placement testing at NMEC

AR scenes preparation

After the detection phase we starting preparing the AR scenes compiling stories that are relevant to the artifacts and their origins. The first artifact we chose was the Nubian House, the idea was to reveal the beauty of the Nubian houses as they are famous for their vibrant colors and hand-drawn symbols, the Nubia is also famous for its authentic music and the mock-up presented in the museum is completely grey and doesn't replicate the Nubian atmosphere at all.

Figure 52 on the left the Nubian house presented in the museum, on the right the Nubian houses in real life

Initially it was planned to replicates the 3d model of the Nubian doorway and colorize its symbols and add annotations that explain the meaning of the Nubian symbols and the story behind their choices of colors, the design evolution of the façade can be found below, it evolved from [2d image](#) into a more detailed [3d models](#) that covers the mock-up facade in the museum properly after several testing and modifications that were done on the model.

Figure 53 Diagram that illustrates the Nubian facade design evolution and testing at the museum

After working on the façade and based on the literature review, we realized that contextualization of the artifact's-built environment helped in the memorability and the informal learning related to it so we decided to add a context to the façade and create a full Nubian environment, that depends on surface placement and not image targeting to facilitate the revealing of the whole environment. during the [first iteration](#) we just added some palm trees then during the [second one](#) we added a terrain and some Nubian music but the scene was too heavy, i.e. it had a large number of polygons and triangles to run on mobile phones as an AR scene and it lagged a lot so we needed to optimize it and we removed the terrain to ensure the smooth running of the experience which is found in [iteration 3](#) which was used in the game later. The full Nubian House scene before the removal of the terrain can be found in the following link: <https://youtu.be/pdH5xTsFPDE>

Figure 54 Diagram of the Nubian House Environment Progression

The second monument we worked on is the Description of Egypt book the idea behind it was to enable the visitor to see different pages of the book, since it's always exhibited on the same page and to hear a narration of its content. A character was chosen to narrate a small part of the book's content whilst animating the virtual book pages in the AR scene (*creating a flipping pages in the AR*), During the First Iteration the narration of the was in English but the museum administrators recommended that we switch it into Arabic in the Final iteration and to make the character look more Egyptian, the full AR scene can be found in the following Link:

<https://youtu.be/u7VK4KJ7cSE>

Figure 55 the Description of Egypt Book Design Progression

The third artifact was the Sabil we wanted to show the mechanism of the Sabil and its function as its main function is to provide street passengers with water, it has an underground water reserve and its upper floors act as “Kuttab” which is a small school that teaches children The Holy Quran. We created an animation of the water mechanism which can be found in the following link: https://youtu.be/jShGqWW1N_A and then in the final iteration we added the annotations of the Sabil elements to educate people about them.

Figure 56 The Sabil Design Progression

Moving to the secondary artifacts we have changed some of our initial selection of the artifacts to include items that are widely distributed in the museum hall and represent all the civilizations. So that each era contains at least two artifacts in the scavenger hunt, with the intention to include more than 3 in the future to fulfill the game rules.

The below diagram illustrated the final artifacts selected and their location in the museum main hall. The hunt shall start from the predynastic era with the key of life moving towards the rest of the civilizations to ensure the visitors engagement with the different eras presented at the museum.

Ptolemaic / Roman , Byzantine and Coptic eras

Niobe statue

Mosaic Floor

Kingdoms era

Harp

Chair

Amon's Wife Statue

Predynastic & Archaic Era

Key of Life

Ships & Boats

Islamic Caliphate

Kiswa

Sabil

Egyptian Heritage

Nubian House

Description of Egypt Book

NMEC Main Hall

Figure 57 The final artifacts selected for the scavenger hunt and their locations in the main hall

Different multimedia components were added to the artifacts scenes to test which ones would better communicate to the public for instance; the AR scenes of the Key of life, the ships and the chair are static 3d renders of the models, For the harp it's a 3d model accompanied by an audio music of the harp itself, in the case of the statues of Amon's wife and Niobe AI was used to manipulated their faces to make them come to life and have actual facial expressions like a smile for instance, this was done using [myheritage](#) AI engine. Moving to the Mosaic floor we decided to do a virtual reconstruction of the artifact and for the Kiswa¹⁰ which has a huge religious value and includes some verses of the Holy Quran on it, we decided to add a recitation audio of one of the verses with a translation of the verse from Arabic to English to make it accessible to non-Arabic speakers. Regarding the AR targeting of the artifacts, the Key of life, the mosaic floor, the Kiswa image targeting of the monuments themselves are used for AR detection, however regarding the harp and the ship due their complex structure and strong details, it was not possible to use their images as targets instead the accompanied info tags and the posters of the monuments themselves are used as markers for their AR scenes. As for the chair and the statues their AR scenes were prepared and to be executed in the future as their image targets are yet to be chosen. The following diagrams illustrate the artifacts and their target images and their accompanied rendered AR scenes and hyperlinks to their AR testing.

The Artifact	The Image Target	AR output
Key of Life		

¹⁰ The Kiswa is considered the Curtain of the Holy Kaaba, and the one found at NMEC represents a Kiswa that was manufactured in Egypt and sent to Saudi Arabia.

The Artifact

The Image Target

AR output

Raft /Ship

[Harp](#)

The Artifact	The Image Target	AR output
	<p data-bbox="597 768 857 808">Amon's Wife Statue</p> <p data-bbox="597 930 870 970"><i>Yet to be determined</i></p>	<p data-bbox="906 930 1312 970">https://youtu.be/vE7wo24vOTI</p>
	<p data-bbox="597 1119 769 1159">Niobe Statue</p> <p data-bbox="597 1281 870 1320"><i>Yet to be determined</i></p>	<p data-bbox="906 1281 1312 1320">https://youtu.be/tNrqZZNO-88</p>

The Artifact

The Image Target

AR output

[The Mosaic Floor](#)

<https://youtube.com/shorts/FXtk2vpRSJg?feature=share>

[Kiswa](#)

After the scenes preparations it was time to compile AUGI’s mobile application prototype which was created by Mirhan Ayman, to further engage the users. It was planned to allow the players to create their own avatars to personalize their experience further but due to time limitations the working MVP only has the name, age and email user registration at the beginning, the game starts with user onboarding screens explaining the game, moving to the user registration, then to the treasure map which includes all the artifacts included in the game with some hints about the monuments and their location in the museum hall to facilitate the treasure hunt, after the players scan any treasure and see the AR scene they must click on “Collect treasure” button in order to gain points and move to the next artifact, the players are free to choose which artifacts they chase first, and after they collect them they reach the end the game and get a claim your gift screen. Hence entertaining and motivating the museum visitors. The following diagram illustrates a few of AUGI mobile screens. The full experience can be found in the link below:

<https://youtu.be/RsuN17vby3c>

Figure 58 AUGI onboarding screens

Registration screen

Hints example

Annotations example

Finishing and Gift screens

Figure 59 A selection of AUGI Prototype screens

Conclusion and Future Work

The project has successfully implemented most of the CHx framework features whether in the design and planning stage or the MVP stage proving that the framework can actually be applied inside museums and that its features allow the creation of novel experiences. One of AUGI's restrictions was the museum environment itself although it was rich of opportunities to create interactive innovative multimedia that would engage and entertain the visitors, the decisions about the project implementation phase were a bit slow. However, it shows its potential for application outside the walls of the museum as well because it can be used to bring historical streets and buildings to life, engaging the public more with CH found in their daily surrounding environments. Imagine create a treasure map on the scale of a city with treasures located in various places and streets! This would definitely turn the city into a touristic destination.

Different artifacts in the treasure map required different approaches to bring them to life which allowed the implementation of various visual multimedia communication techniques with the intention to test their effect on the users to determine the techniques favored by the users and the reasons behind that.

The initial prototype of AUGI was done in English with the plan to include the option for Arabic and other languages later on.

Since AUGI was a group project it was challenging but successful to tackle the CH experience, AI, cultural preservation and Egyptian monuments in one project which were the initial interests of the researchers. The diversity of interest allowed for the deeper of the project and the usage of various tools to create the Virtual scenes, the AR experience itself and to create the mobile application, the following diagram represents the project's architecture:

Figure 60 AUGI's Architecture

Regarding AR technology it was learnt that Image targeting works better with 2d images or planar simple 3d objects and for more complex 3d objects the targeting would require the 3d scanning of the objects themselves to use them as object targets.

AUGI would play a role in reviving the museum artifacts and helping the visitors learn about the monuments without a tour guide. AUGI withholds a great potential for future work for instance all the main hall artifacts can be included in the hunt giving the players more freedom in choosing their treasures, a second level of the game can be added by including the other museum halls to the game. Furthermore, the project can be used as a pilot case study and be implemented in other museums. Also, at the moment the running mobile version is for Android and there are plans for developing the game for IOS as well.

The creation of AUGI and the image targets dataset enabled players to visit a selected number of NMEC artifacts from anywhere making CH and data more accessible.

You can scan the QR code below to download AUGI and use the image targets mentioned before in order to enjoy the virtual accessible gamified multisensory CH experience using AR

Chapter 5

c[AR]ds

The Process

Introduction

C[AR]ds is a conceptual design done in this research in attempt to apply most features of the CHx framework features outside the context of museums with the focus on olfactory and haptic sensory. It illustrates an opportunity to create a multisensory card game that reveals AR virtual scenes upon scanning and can contain any CH data inside and outside the context in Egypt. C[AR]ds also present an opportunity for educational card games that can be adopted by any of the SLAMs institutes globally as any material can be added to the c[AR]d. The prototype of the c[AR] is to be created in the near future by the researcher.

Figure 62 represents the features of the CHx framework used in this experiment while Figure 63 uses the shape to highlight the similar features implemented in this experiment and the previous two.

Figure 61 [CHx] framework features used in c[AR]ds

Figure 62[CHx] framework features used in c[AR]ds with the highlighted features applied in the previous experiments

The above diagram shows that technology, interaction, fulfillment and entertainment sections are mostly similar to the living painting and AUGI's experiments and that multimedia communication is the main feature that is notably different from the previous experiments. For instance, the cards are added to the non-tech physical multimedia which include CH scenes or artifacts and the card itself is measured by the appropriateness of the card size, the material used (paper quality, if paper is used so that it doesn't wear or get torn easily) and the quality of the illustrations on the card.

In case of mixed media visual data is transformed into tactile cards of by using materials of different thickness to present the artifacts or by using 3d printing to imprint artifacts on the cards or by using braille text. In addition to creating interactive nodes on the cards inspired by the (Tooteko) project mentioned earlier, that generate sound and narration of the artifact once pressed by the player to further engage people with vision and illiteracy issues, transforming visual media into sound. Tangible data is also transformed into olfactory data by using scented papers that complement the eras and the scenes presented on each card. Transforming what's heard into something to be seen is done by including subtitles and text to any sound included. And finally authentic food should be served whilst playing the game that reflect the culture and the atmosphere of the cards used. The success of these transformed data is measured by the level of inclusion of people with hearing, vision and illiteracy issues that choose to play the game and their scale of comprehending the information thoroughly.

This game is still in early ideation stage and requires further development in the game play and mechanism, however it successfully adapts most of the CHx framework with the potential to include it all with further development.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The concept of CH, its digitalization and designing its experiences is a complex topic because it has so many intersecting sub-concepts and although the researcher has succeeded in creating a holistic CH experience framework based on analyzing the literature review that combined aspects of accessibility, gamification, multisensory design and enjoyable informal learning in CH using AR, there is a lot to be investigated regarding the subject because the change in any variable might lead to the change of others.

The framework created relies on technological solutions, the human interaction and the human response as its three main pillars from which the main concepts of the CHx framework are derived which are technology, multimedia communication, interaction, motivation, fulfillment and enjoyment. Which meant that a human centered approach should be taken into consideration in order to create a holistic CH experience.

The selected features to create the framework are to be tested and validated by the experts through various surveys and interviews in order to include or eliminate the required features that would enable the guideline usage by designers globally in designing CH experiences in the near future.

The implementation of the framework on the three experiments outlined proved the possibility of its application in different CH contexts, inside and outside museums and the potential it has for implementation outside the context of Egyptian CH.

It was challenging to include all the framework sub-features in the designs of the experiments however at least one sub-feature of each main concept was used. Which showed flexibility in the framework usage and its adaptability to be included different projects.

The experiments indicated that the Egyptian CH presents a fruitful environment to create innovative designs and although due to time constraints no formal surveys nor interviews were done on users and participants of the conducted experiments, during the creation of Living Paintings ad AUGI and testing their virtual experiences, the preliminary comments and response of the passersby

and the observers inside the museums were highly positive, they were impressed by the ideas and wanted to see the final output.

There's a huge gap in the digital archiving of CH elements in Egypt that needs to be addressed because without the digital preservation our history is at danger of being lost.

Since the experiments call for inclusive and accessible design, I would like to include people with hearing and vision impairments and people with illiteracy issues in the future surveys in order to make modifications in both the experiments and the CHx framework itself to make it more inclusive.

The art of storytelling combined with the appropriate multimedia has the power to bring history to life. Which made me think why don't we do that more often? I enjoyed combining various multimedia techniques with various artifacts to create a certain message and I have learnt that the output product must be coordinated with the end gadget, meaning not everything will run smoothly on a cellphone.

I also appreciated the notion of transformable data and how data can be transformed to accommodate different sensory receptors which is a concept that I would like to further explore in the future.

This research has enabled me to explore AR technology deeply which became a huge interest of mine that I would like to explore its potentials in the future as well as other extended reality technologies like virtual reality and mixed reality because I think they really have the ability to transform any experience.

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